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Sustainability for Thai Nguyen Province

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to research on sustainable livelihoods, overview of research related to sustainable livelihoods, studies in Thai Nguyen Vietnam. Since then, finding research gaps and researching to develop policy solutions to support sustainable livelihoods for people in Thai Nguyen province, Vietnam.

Keywords: Sustainable livelihoods, Thai Nguyen, Vietnam

1. Introduction

In the world and in Vietnam, there have been many studies on sustainable livelihoods in both theory and practice. Most studies show that unsustainable livelihoods are due to the heavy dependence on exploitation of natural resources, reducing biodiversity and reducing resources, and lack of autonomy in resources. livelihoods [40], [59], [72]. Some studies on sustainable livelihoods in the buffer zone conduct assessment of livelihood resources, thereby identifying the advantages and limitations of resources for the implementation of sustainable livelihood activities [57], [65], [14], [17], [22]. Newer studies have used an index scale to measure livelihood security, livelihood sustainability [32], [47], [31], [68], [64], [51]. Local and national research has different ways of assessing sustainable livelihoods, but most studies also focus on analyzing the status of livelihood resources; performance assessment of livelihoods; from there, identify results and goals of livelihood implementation. However, most of the research on sustainable livelihoods in the buffer zone do not have a clear assessment criteria system, the scales are inconsistent, the number and quality of research indicators depends on the opinion of the owner. Therefore, there are many different assessment results about sustainable livelihoods.

On the other hand, according to planners and policymakers, the Thai Nguyen Livelihood Area is under threat of biodiversity and conservation resources by 13 threats [27], of which most of them are related to livelihood activities of people in the buffer zone, this is also the cause of unsustainable development in the buffer zone. The core issue that local agencies and governments need to pay attention to is the socio-economic development of the buffer zone while conserving resources, in which the conservation and maintenance of natural resources is an important issue in the current context.

Facing that fact, policy makers have paid attention to the implementation of institutional and policy towards promoting livelihood resources for the buffer zone residents, creating opportunities for residents to implement sustainable livelihood activities. However, the implementation and application efficiency in the Buffer Zone of the Livelihood Zone in general and Thai Nguyen in particular has not been as expected, the results of the implementation of livelihoods of residents are still limited and unsustainable. Up to now, there is still no comprehensive study on the issue of sustainable livelihoods of Thai Nguyen residents.

2. Literature review

2.1. Some sustainable livelihood studies based on the advantages of local livelihood resources

Based on the advantages of local livelihood resources to improve, transform or develop livelihood activities, studies have developed or used an analytical framework as a research method. .

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Teresa – Chang Hung Tao (2006), Fujun Shen (2009) [71], [75] identified tourism as a sustainable livelihood strategy for communities living in Taiwan, China. Research shows that the advantage of resources for tourism development is the basis for the purpose of changing livelihoods and improving unsustainable livelihood activities in the agricultural and rural sector. From there, the locality needs to implement policies to support livelihood transformation. Research shows that implementing sustainable tourism livelihoods must combine the intersection of “sustainable rural livelihoods; Sustainable Tourism; Rural tourism ”. In which, institutional capital is considered as other sources of livelihood capital, this is also the biggest difference of the study compared with DFID (1999) [71].

Muhammad Asiful Basar (2009) in Bangladesh focuses on land resources, assuming that five land groups of different sizes will have different advantages for livelihood development options, while performing an analysis of the five sources. livelihood capital to identify strengths and weaknesses according to local living standards. The result is four different levels of income [59].

Thus, the above studies focus on analyzing the advantages of livelihood activities on the basis of water resources, land resources, scenic spots ... to evaluate the advantages and limitations of these activities. livelihoods, point out livelihood results, from that give implications for policies and solutions to develop sustainable livelihoods. However, these studies only assess individual livelihood activities, the research context focuses on more than 70% of people participating in fisheries activities, or some subjects who are trained and capable. investment, lack of community (except the poor) [46], or value natural resources [59].

2.2. Some studies on sustainable livelihoods in the buffer zone are based on the use of influencing factors model

These studies focus on the use of influence factor models to assess the relationship between factors affecting livelihood activities, but mainly those that depend on natural resources of the reserve. subsistence or livelihood zones such as:

Obong Linus Beba et al. (2013) analyzed the livelihood status of the buffer zone at Cross River Livelihoods. The study shows that the livelihood activities of the people in the buffer zone affect the livelihood area, in which agricultural production encroaching on forest land accounts for 20%; poaching 15.2%; harvesting medicinal herbs 6.4%; logging 3.6% and other activities 12.8%. These activities are influenced by factors of exploitation scale, cultivated land area, education level, gender of the household head ... [63]. Teija Reyes (2008) identified traditional agricultural and forestry activities of the buffer zone people could have more positive changes if the local authorities have appropriate policies such as: (1) Regulatory forest management. participation of people to enhance the role of natural resource management; (2) Changing people's awareness through the complete political institutions of the organization in enhancing the role of agriculture and forestry in poverty reduction. These livelihood activities differ from one locality to another due to the distance from the residence to the nature reserve, land size, income, food ...; Of which, only 6% of people surveyed said there was no decrease in productivity; 65% of respondents think a decrease due to climate change and a 19% decrease in productivity due to environmental degradation. The reasons for the above results are lack of capital (37%), lack of market (37%), lack of training (37%), lack of awareness (37%), lack of fertilizer (33%), lack of people. force (28%), lack of arable land (12%) and the reliability of this interpretation is up to 73% [66].

Taruvunga. A and Mushunje. A (2015) provides 4 Tobit regression models with 11 factors affecting the probability that people will participate in combined exploitation of NTFPs. The results of the 4 models reflect the combination (number of species) of non-timber forest products harvested that will affect different forest resources and protected areas. In which, the factors of population and household demographics account for 73% [78].

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The approach to livelihood sustainability analysis of the studies shows that: livelihood sustainability is reflected in terms of economic, social, environmental and institutional structure and policy processes. . These criteria allow a comprehensive assessment of negative and positive impacts on the sustainability of livelihoods.

Bruce K. Downie (2015) uses the intended behavioral theory to explore the behavior of the people in the Saadani National Park buffer zone on the possibility of livelihood expansion or transformation as well as long-term production goals. Since then, there are four recommendations that should change a part, increase resources, maintain the status quo or replace a new livelihood. The four livelihood areas that buffer zone people participate in include resource-dependent livelihoods, wage income, business activities and other sources [38]. Lamsal et al. (2015) indicated that income from extraction of protected area resources accounted for 12.4% of total household income [56].

Winin Zakiah et al. (2015) studied sustainable livelihoods in the buffer zone of Sebangau livelihood area, which is a peat swamp area. The study assesses the current status of 5 livelihoods capital sources and thinks that 5 livelihood capital sources all affect all people's livelihood activities, these five capital sources are also developed as the main indicator of their approach. framework for livelihood analysis. The research results show that fishermen in the buffer zone have very low access to capital for economic development, at around 50%. The author also stated that the sustainable dimension of real livelihood must be based on criteria of environmental, social, economic, and structural sustainability and the institutional process going in the direction of enhancing the sustainable livelihood activities [80]. This is considered a case study on sustainable livelihoods of people in the buffer zone.

These studies only focus on analyzing the factor model of the influence of traditional livelihoods and livelihoods dependent on resources Livelihood zones, factors that only reflect the size of capital. human, natural, social, financial in some livelihood activities; or comes from unsustainable exploitation and unclear institutional and policy processes. The objective of the study is to clarify the advantages of mining operations with little negative impacts on the livelihoods resources [63]. The study also identified the factors that greatly affect the exploitation scale and the number of species to be exploited [76]. Survey method of intended behavior is considered a significant qualitative method for planning and orienting in sustainable livelihood development [38]. Winin Zakiah et al (2015) clarified the criteria for assessing livelihood sustainability and considered the role of the five livelihood capital sources to reflect all the development of livelihood activities, besides That study also pointed out the size of livelihood sustainability based on 4 criteria assessing environmental sustainability, economic sustainability, social sustainability and institutional and policy sustainability [80].

However, the above studies only focus on analyzing the factor models affecting some traditional livelihood activities, focusing on livelihoods dependent on natural resources for a number of livelihood activities. In addition, there is no complete theoretical framework as a basis for assessing sustainable livelihoods in the buffer zone, the system of research indicators and methods of sustainable livelihood assessment is not clear.

2.3. Some research on sustainable livelihoods is based on the use of indicators to measure sustainable livelihoods

Recently, many studies on sustainable livelihoods have used synthetic indicators to measure sustainability in livelihoods. The first index-based sustainable livelihood assessments were used by CARE in India and Sri Lanka between 1995 and 1997. CARE introduced the Security Livelihoods Index_SLI for the index's purpose of to provide more clarity on the constraints on the livelihood security of poor rural households.

Up to now, this index has been used by many studies to evaluate such as: Suresh Kumara & A. Raizadaa & H. Biswasa (2014) [73], Lindenberg (2002) [57], Saijad Haroon, et al. (2010) [68]. The index measures based on five aspects: economic security, food security, health safety, educational security and decentralization (Lindenberg, 2002), and the development of the index's components is used. as studied by Hahn et al. (2009)

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[44]. CARE said that, to develop a set of indicators to evaluate each household based on meetings and related discussions of a number of non-governmental organizations (CARE, 2004). This construction is based on the survey of data from the development of livelihood security indicators, rural rapid assessment (CARE, 2004).

Mical B. Hahn (2009) built the livelihood vulnerability index (LVI) on the basis of analyzing the negative effects of climate change, the author pointed out 8 components including: ethnic information, demographics, health, social relationships, food, water resources, natural damage and climate change with 28 assessment indicators [44]. Kumar Lamichane (2010) shows 44 indicators based on 13 main components of five livelihood capital sources. The vulnerability index is a combination of 3 component indices (expression, susceptibility and adaptive capacity index). The results show that 8/13 components have a vulnerability index of more than 0.5, the highest vulnerability of financial capital (0.7), human and natural resources have the higher vulnerability index. 0.5. Calculation formula: $VLI = \sum VI (Hi) / \sum wi$. (where VI is the index of component injury; wi is weighted) [55]. Thus, livelihoods adapting to climate change will be those with less risk, more resilience than other livelihoods and show that the livelihood diversification strategy is the best method to limit the risk.

Currently, the use of indicators to measure sustainable livelihoods is approached in many different aspects, in which the use of the sustainable livelihood security index, the sustainable livelihood index is considered as an indicator. Social is most important for assessing quality of life, reflecting the response to basic human needs, and at the same time expressing the limitations of a household's ability to increase well-being and development.

Pramod K. Singh *, B.N. Hiremath (2010) [64] identified indicators based on three criteria: ecological security, economic efficiency and social equity. In which, (1) Ecological security includes: forest cover, water quality, potential increase, habits and potential for groundwater regeneration; (2) Economic efficiency: total grain yield (kg / ha); milk yield per animal (kg / day), ratio of sowing area (%); (3) Social equity: employment rate (%), literate female rate (%), mothers' survival rate (%). Anisul Haque, M. Shah Alam Khan et al. (2016) evaluated the sustainable livelihood security indicators of coastal households in Bangladesh also based on 5 different components: (1) Food, (2) import, (3) Life & health, (4) Home & property and (5) Water security [32].

Shaheen Akter and Sanzidur Rahman (2012) [31] said that issues of economic security, food, nutrition, health, education, empowerment, environmental safety, ... affect the ability to measure the sustainability of livelihoods. Each indicator is measured on a different scale, indicators are standardized according to different metrological approaches. Roslina Kamaruddin et al (2014) used the sustainable livelihood index as a tool to assess the viability of livelihoods based on 5 capital sources (natural, human, physical, social, financial) and the livelihood outcomes factor. SLI evaluation results are based on Hahn partners (2009): $LSI = \{[(Index H * wH) + (Index P * wP) + (Index S * wS) + (Index F * wF) + (Index N * wN)]: [wH + wP + wS + wF + wN]\}$ (wi is the sub-factor of each major factor). The results show that the SLI is lower than 0.5 and indicates that not all high-income households have high SLI [51].

Haroon Sajjad & I. Nasreen (2016) [69] studied and evaluated the sustainability level in agriculture based on 3 criteria: ecological security, economic efficiency and social equity with 15 indicators. The study used Pearson regression analysis and correlation analysis to determine the degree of the link between the Sustainable Livelihoods Security Index with the component indicators. The results show that the correlation between SLSI and the economic efficiency index is very high; between SLSI and the social equity index is important and high. Regression analysis of the beta coefficient of economic efficiency and social equity at 99%. The value of R2 in economic efficiency is highest (0.829) followed by social equity (0.759). Therefore, it can be concluded that the sustainable livelihood security of farmers depends more on economic efficiency and social equity. According to the survey results, 33% of people have a high livelihood index, 31% are very low, 28% are sustainable at an average level, of which 7% have a high level of sustainable livelihoods. Heyuan You and Xiaoling Zhang (2017) use 16 criteria to calculate weights according to vector calculation method. The results show that the

differences in the level of sustainability in the three dimensions of ecology, economic efficiency and social updates of 31 provinces are different [47].

Thus, the indicators for assessing the level of sustainable livelihoods are used by many authors and increasingly complete the set of assessment indicators based on five resources, livelihood results, detailed analysis and quality. in the scale of reasonable choice. The study of indicators allows to evaluate in a comprehensive and comprehensive way the aspects on many different scales. However, the limitation of this type of research is that most of them are qualitatively measured, the number of questions or indicators can be decisive to increase the reliability of information from the perspective of related issues. On the other hand, the above studies were carried out in many different contexts, and different index analysis approaches should lead to different quantity, size and quality of indicators selected for measurement. Besides, the determination of the weighting method for different studies is not the same, so there are many results.

2.4. Overview of research on sustainable livelihoods in the country

Domestic livelihood research was conducted in the 1990s, first focusing on poverty reduction in rural areas of Vietnam, ethnic minorities. Support for livelihood development through rural development projects aims to improve the lives of the poor, increase access to social services, education and health ... The support is still subsidized, leading to the fact that many regions become dependent, work efficiency and productivity have not changed much. When the project is over, the poor in upland and remote areas have returned to their old habits. Ineffective support activities have not been improved. Therefore, the issue of building and selecting sustainable livelihoods for rural people, especially ethnic minorities, is concerned by many authors.

Dang Thi Kim Phung (2012) [65], research on livelihoods of people in the buffer zone in Lo Go Xa Mat Livelihood Area. The survey of 150 households showed that there are 23 main livelihood activities, of which 5 agricultural activities and 18 non-agricultural activities. Main livelihood activities include cultivation, animal husbandry, labor and wages. The research results on 4 groups of households (rich, fair, medium, poor) show that the current status of human capital is low, only 46%, the rich and 33% the better-off; 23% of the poor; illiteracy rate is high 32%; The majority of people with university degrees are rich and well-off households; Only 6% of household heads have agricultural production techniques; The rich own 3-4 times more land than the poor, and up to 33% of the surveyed households do not have land and are mainly engaged in wage employment. In addition, the poor are also at a disadvantage in accessing capital because of lack of land assets, 84% of the poor, 83% of the near poor and 54% of the better off households still live in temporary houses. Nguyen Dang Hiep Pho (2016) when studying the livelihoods of Chau Ma people in the buffer zone of Cat Tien Livelihood Zone also analyzed the strengths and weaknesses of 5 sources of livelihood capital: (1) Human capital includes: team medical team, medical facility, educational and educational background; (2) Social capital: social network, mass organization relationship, borrowing relationship; (3) Physical capital: electricity, roads, schools, stations; (4) Financial capital including subsidies...; (5) Natural capital [22].

Nguyen Xuan Hoa (2018) [17] studying the livelihoods of San Diu people in the buffer zone of Tam Dao Livelihood Zone, the author pointed out that the San Diu people's income from 6 livelihood activities includes: (1) Fields, (2) Home gardens, (3) Forest gardens, (4) Income from livestock raising, (5) Poultry raising, (6) Self-harvesting, average gross income of livestock a household is VND 12.5 million in 2016. In addition, the study uses the method of comparing criteria over time before and after the establishment of the Livelihood Zone to clarify the possibility of changing livelihood activities. design of people in the buffer zone. Meanwhile, the study of Dinh Thi Ha Giang (2017) [14] in the resident community in the buffer zone of Xuan Son Livelihood Zone shows that the main source of income is from farming and husbandry activities, with 88 9% have incomes below 1 million / month / person. The study also pointed out 5 sources of livelihood capital that people in the buffer zone of Xuan Son Livelihood Zone show, that the livelihood capital is poor. Livelihoods sustainability

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assessment studies are divided into 4 levels: (1) Not yet sustainable; (2) low level sustainability; (3) moderately sustainable; and (4) high level of sustainability and more than 50% of the targets set are unsustainable.

Thus, studies on livelihoods in the Buffer Zone in the Livelihood Area focus on analyzing the current status of resources of livelihood activities, evaluating and comparing the results of livelihoods, assessing the status and advantages of the livelihood activities. livelihood resources before and after the establishment of livelihood zones [20], or based on the status of results achieved with the set goals [14], some other studies evaluate livelihood resources among groups households [17], [14], [65]. However, the studies only stop at assessing the status of livelihood resources, the results of livelihood activities, not clarifying the basis for assessing the sustainability of livelihoods as well as not yet available. system of criteria and indicators to measure the level of sustainable livelihoods.

Dang Dinh Dao et al (2014) building a sustainable livelihood analysis model for ethnic minorities in Quang Nam province. The study assesses the resources that directly affect the five livelihood activities, including cultivation, animal husbandry, handicraft, trade and service and other livelihood models. Since then, the advantages of farming livelihood resources are identified as a conditional industry and advantages over other livelihood activities, which is the main income generating industry for people. In particular, institutions and policies positively impact all aspects of people's lives but also create the idea of relying on change, lack of courage to improve livelihoods and household incomes [13]. Phan Xuan Linh (2015) also builds a model of sustainable livelihoods for ethnic minorities in Dak Lak province, consisting of three main components: livelihood capital as the center is affected by institutions, policies and challenges. sustainability awareness (economic, environmental, social). Livelihood strategies mentioned include: agriculture, non-agriculture, diversification [18].

Nguyen Dang Hao (2016) conducted an assessment of resources and livelihood outcomes of 5 livelihood activities including: based on agriculture; combine agriculture with professions and services; aquaculture-based strategy; mixed strategy. The basis for determining evaluation criteria is based on the theoretical framework of Ellis (2000) and Scoones (1998) [16]. While Vu Thi Hoai Thu (2012) gives indicators that reflect the positive impacts of climate change on four specific livelihood activities, including fishing, farming, collection, processing, and agricultural production. , based on 5 evaluation criteria including economic, social, environmental, institutional and climate change adaptive factors [25].

Vo Van Tuan and Le Canh Dung (2015) [27] used Tobit regression model to evaluate 10 influencing factors (social capital, financial capital, physical capital, labor skills, rice land, land crops, land for shrimp, indicators of livelihood diversification (%) ... to the ability to diversify agricultural livelihoods.

Research Nguyen Minh Thu (2013), is considered the first study in Vietnam to establish a sustainable development index based on the expenditure system of sustainable development assessment in Vietnam. The component indexes include aggregate index, social index, and environmental aspects. The index measures the level of sustainability based on the time comparison, the weight determined for the component indexes by expert method [30]. However, this study has a secondary, inconsistent data set at the household level, at a macro level reflecting sustainable development.

Thus, as well as other studies in the world, research in Vietnam focuses on assessing the current state of capital and clarifying sustainability criteria, some studies have demonstrated the diversification of livelihoods for the strategy. sustainable livelihoods. This is also proven in the case studies of Scoones (1998), F. Ellis (2000).

The recent index method is widely used and diversified, especially used to assess sustainable livelihoods as an effective tool and can overcome the limitations of many other methods. However, the use of the index method still has certain limitations as mentioned above (there are no clear indicators and scales of sustainable livelihood assessment, the comments given are lack of grounds. and lack of credibility). In Vietnam, there are no studies

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using indicators to measure the level of sustainable livelihoods of residents in the Buffer Zone at the household level. The problem of using indicators to measure the level of sustainable livelihoods in Vietnam is still limited. Some studies use vulnerability index to assess livelihood sustainability [27], but the assessment aspect reflects the negative side of influencing factors and information collected is oriented. Therefore, this approach is not suitable for assessing the multi-faceted livelihood and many livelihood activities.

3. Overview of livelihood studies in Thai Nguyen

Currently, there are no independent studies on sustainable livelihoods for people in the buffer zone of Thai Nguyen Livelihood Zone. Some studies approach livelihoods on the basis of assessing the current situation of livelihood activities affecting conservation or developing new livelihood models without forgetting the possibility that people can take action. that livelihood for a long time.

Rita Gebert and Trang Hieu Tuong (2011) studied the relationship between gender and poverty, identified the sex of the household head, the equality of women in the family, the proportion of women in the family and the status of hunger. poor people. The results show that men have the right to make decisions about livelihood activities in the family, gender inequality in decisions on livelihood activities still exists [15].

The report on the Socio-Economic Development Plan of the Buffer Zone towards Conservation of Thai Nguyen Livelihood Area to 2020, vision to 2030 by Thai Nguyen Provincial People's Committee in cooperation with GIZ (2014) points out the basic features in terms of socio-economic issues, local resource distribution in the buffer zone of Thai Nguyen Livelihood Area, advantages and limitations for each livelihood activity. In addition, the study provides forecasts about socio-economic problems of the buffer zone up to 2020 such as income, food, land, labor, population, livestock ownership, ... allows the author to give an overview of the socio-economic situation in the buffer zone, the livelihood activities that the buffer zone people participate in [28].

Christian Schoen, Mesopartner (2014) [5] implementing selection of priority livelihoods to support. Livelihoods capital sources are assessed using the teambuilding method, identifying evaluation criteria on economic, environmental and social efficiency for six selected livelihood activities to prioritize and 10 livelihood models, including five assessment models achieved a scale of 7/10 points in all three aspects. Pham Thanh Luong (2016) makes a planning process for implementing livelihood support for 4 livelihood groups, proposing implementation support in accordance with conservation requirements, maintaining biodiversity and cultural factors. clan. However, the study does not provide a basis for evaluating livelihood activities [58].

Explanation on the Master Plan on conservation, embellishment and promotion of the value of special national monuments, Thai Nguyen Livelihood Area for the period 2016 - 2025 and vision 2035 shows the conditions and advantages of resources in Tourism development is associated with the task of preserving and embellishing the special values of the livelihood zone. The report identifies the characteristics of the impact of population, labor, awareness, topography as well as livelihood activities that people in the buffer zone are operating in the core zone on the conservation of Livelihoods. . Since then, proposing policies to supplement infrastructure, water systems, support people to transform their non-agricultural livelihoods, especially people in the core zone are ethnic people who are heavily dependent on natural resources [first].

4. Conclusion

Firstly, research on sustainable livelihoods is not a new topic, but in the context of the Buffer Zone of the Livelihood Zone, especially for Thai Nguyen residents, there is no comprehensive study on this issue. . This is therefore a matter of practical significance for residents of the buffer zone and the conservation goal of the Livelihood Zone provides a clearer comprehensive picture of the current livelihood status and level of livelihood sustainability of the people. People, from there, propose appropriate solutions and policy implications for enhancing sustainable livelihoods in the Buffer Zone of the Livelihood Zone.

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Secondly, the research and analysis of sustainable livelihoods in general and sustainable livelihoods in the Buffer Zone of Livelihoods in particular are still separate, there is no clear assessment criteria system, there is no framework. / separate analysis model for the livelihoods of residents in the Buffer Zone of the Livelihood Area. The evaluation results also depend on the quantity and quality of the research indicators and scales of the authors, leading to dissimilar results. Some other studies, analyze the status of livelihood resources in-depth and use the model to evaluate the relationship between livelihoods and influencing factors, from which subjective judgment on livelihood activities. In recent years, many studies on sustainable livelihoods have taken a comprehensive approach to livelihood analysis and offer a variety of methods to assess and measure the sustainability of livelihoods as a comparative method, The index method ... However, the system of defined criteria and indicators depends on the research context and research approach. On the other hand, studies on sustainable livelihoods of residents in the buffer zone, both at home and abroad, have not used the index method to measure the sustainability of their livelihoods.

Third, solutions for sustainable livelihood development in the Buffer Zone of the Livelihood Area are built for each specific context, each specific livelihood activity, so there is a lack of a comprehensive overview of livelihood development. Sustainable Buffer Zone Livelihoods in a Conservation Context. Although the study on sustainable livelihoods of Thai Nguyen residents, although only set in the context of the Buffer Zone of the Livelihood Zone, the study will provide more clarity about the research indicator system, the sustainable livelihood analysis model of buffer zone residents, methods of resource assessment and measurement of sustainable livelihoods.

Stemming from the above problems, the researcher found that it was a research gap that previously not done by foreign and domestic authors, especially for residents of the buffer zone of the Livelihood Zone, Thai Nguyen on that basis, proposing solutions and policy implications to enhance sustainable livelihoods for residents in the buffer zone of Thai Nguyen Livelihood Zone in the context of implementing the goal of conserving livelihoods and promoting the advantages of resources.

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